

“THE IMPACT OF SEISMIC WAVES FROM EXPLOSIONS ON UNDERGROUND MINE WORKINGS AND SURFACE MINING COMPLEXES”

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The increase in production capacity and the rapid pace of ore extraction require the extensive use of mass blasting on a large scale. The seismic impact of blasts on buildings and structures is determined by the physico-mechanical properties of the rocks that make up the massif where blasting operations are carried out. When major underground workings, engineering structures, and mine surface facilities are located close to blast sites, it becomes necessary to limit charge sizes, which reduces the effectiveness of blasting and mining operations as well as the production capacity of the mining enterprise.

Taking into account all aspects of the seismic impact of an explosion on underground workings, as well as on surface buildings and structures, is a very difficult task [1]. Under these conditions, it is advisable to obtain an approximate solution to the general problem in order to assess the influence of individual factors and the natural periods of free oscillations and attenuation of seismic waves generated by the explosion [2].

In this case, underground main mine workings and surface structures are considered as a unified elastic system, and the first-order oscillations of these workings and structures under the influence of seismic waves generated by an explosion are studied. The system is assumed to be symmetric with respect to two vertical planes and is modeled as a vertical system with concentrated masses [3].

The foundation of the system undergoes oscillatory polarized motion according to the law of a modulated sinusoid with a frequency characteristic $U(t)$. The displacement of any point in the system relative to the foundation is denoted as $y_k(t)$ and is proportional to the displacement of a pendulum with a natural oscillation period T_0 and a logarithmic decrement of damping λ .

In the case of non-stationary ground vibrations, the seismic effect of explosions on main mine workings and surface structures is determined by the response spectrum. The ordinates of the response spectrum correspond to the maximum displacements of pendulums with different natural oscillation periods and logarithmic decrements of damping.

The response spectrum is expressed as the product of three quantities, namely:

- x_0 — displacement of the standard pendulum, where $T_0=0.25$ and $\lambda=25$;
- ψ — spectral coefficient;
- ε — damping coefficient.

In this case, the formula takes the following form:

$$x = x_0 \cdot \psi \cdot \varepsilon, \quad (1)$$

According to the research findings of S.V. Medvedev [2], the spectral coefficient.

$$\psi = \frac{2}{T_0^2} = T_0^2, \text{ for } 0,5 \text{ sek} \leq T_0 \leq 2 \text{ sek}$$

$$\psi = \frac{1}{T_0^2} = T_0^2, \text{ for } 0,1 \text{ sek} \leq T_0 \leq 0,5 \text{ sek}$$

and the damping coefficient.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\lambda}}, \text{ for } 0,25 \leq \lambda \leq 2.$$

Since the oscillations of a rock mass, which is composed of different types of rocks, are non-stationary, the displacement of the standard pendulum can be determined using segments of seismograms, treating them as oscillations modulated in amplitude and frequency. Under these conditions, by applying the phase-plane method at the Institute of Physics of the Earth of the Russian Academy of Sciences, the displacement of the standard pendulum x was obtained.

$$x_0 = U_{0(m)} \cdot A_0 \quad (2)$$

where $U_{0(m)}$ is the amplitude–frequency characteristic of the standard pendulum, taken according to the data of S.V. Medvedev, depending on the periods of free and forced oscillations [4];

A_0 – is the displacement of the foundation of the standard pendulum.

By substituting expression (2) into equation (1) and dividing it by A_0 , we obtain the amplitude–frequency characteristic for the adopted model used in calculating mine workings, buildings, and structures.

$$U_m = U_{0(m)} \cdot \psi \cdot \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

The amplitude–frequency characteristic, or what is commonly referred to in structural calculations as the dynamic coefficient, provides an understanding of the nature of oscillations of underground mine workings and surface structures in relation to ground vibrations in the vicinity of buildings.

Thus, if the actual seismic shock from an explosion were to generate only monochromatic oscillations of the rocks forming the rock mass, and if these monochromatic oscillations corresponded to the maximum displacements,

velocities, and accelerations, then the dynamic effect of such a shock on the upper parts of mine surface facilities—whose natural oscillation period coincides with the ground oscillation period—would be equal to the values presented in [3].

Analysis of the obtained data [5] shows that the amplitude values of oscillations of underground mine workings and surface structures, under resonance conditions, exceed by several times the amplitudes of oscillations of the rock mass caused by mass explosions. Therefore, when calculating the safe charge weights from the viewpoint of seismic stability, it is necessary to take into account the maximum amplitude characteristics of individual elements of surface structures, as well as the condition and service life of mine workings.

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